

Digitalization in Education with Special Reference to “Swayam”- A Study Web of Active Learning

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Archana, A., et al.
“Digitalization in Education with Special Reference to ‘Swayam’- A Study Web of Active Learning.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 90–96.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575301>

Dr. A. Archana

Professor PG Department, Jain College

BK. Madhukumara & V. Seema

3rd Semester M.A (Economics), Jain College

Abstract

SWAYAM is a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), compatible, open & distance education option which is available through the Information and Communication Technology. It is a new gateway of teaching and learning, initiated by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) helpful from 9th Standard to PG Students. SWAYAM offers 2000 plus courses in different subject domains. This paper is helpful to study the concept of SWAYAM, to study the level of awareness about SWAYAM in and around us. to know how people are enrolling for courses through this platform. The scope of the study has been limited to few college professors and the students.

Keywords: SWAYAM, New Gateway, Online Courses, Communication Technology.

Introduction

Learning is endless process it is womb to tomb, so we can say learning is lifelong process. Open and distance learning (ODL) is a term which accept openness and uses the distance mode for learning. It is one of the most rapidly growing fields of education and its potential has been greatly noticeable through the development of internet based information technology. ODL is a system, where teachers and students need not present at same place or same time also it is so flexible in regard to a method of teaching and learning without compromising necessary qualities. ODL is becoming more and more significant for continuing education, skill developing, and lifelong learning for quality education. SWAYAM is web and mobile based interactive open education interface and courses are available from High school to University level in the form of MOOC.

MOOC (Massive Open online Course) is web based open education platform for unlimited learner participation.

About SWAYAM

SWAYAM is the non-formal educational platform which helps students, teacher, homemakers and all age group of people. The platform was first announced in 2014 and launched in 2017 by

Government of India. The platform has enrolled over 10 million learners. SWAYAM became the largest MOOC provider offering courses to a wide variety of disciplines from prestigious institutions and Universities. 2000 plus courses are available on SWAYAM and also give E-tuitions, E-content like PDF notes, files, video lesson, discussion platform for clearing the doubt and Q&A to evaluate. SWAYAM is for self-actualization providing opportunities in order to ensure that best quality content is produced and delivered. Nine National Coordinators have been approved and as follows.

1. AICTE (All India Council for Technical Education) for self-paced and international courses.
2. NIPTTEL (National Program on Technology Enhanced Learning) for Engineering.
3. UGC (University Grants Commission) for non-technical post-graduation education.
4. CEG (Consortium for Educational Communication) for under-graduate education.
5. NCERT (National Council of Education Research and Training) for school education.
6. NIOS (National Institute of Open Schooling) for school education.
7. IGNOU (Indira Gandhi National Open University) for out of school students.
8. IIMB (Indian Institute of Management, Bengaluru) for management studies.
9. NITTTR (National Institute of Technical Teachers Training and Research) for Teacher Training programme.

Courses delivered through SWAYAM are free of cost to the learner and provide certificate free of cost.

Advantages of SWAYAM

- Free of cost
- Flexibilities in studies
- Best courses availabilities
- Equity and accessibility
- Progress given instantly
- Good faculties and value added courses availability
- Helps competitive exams

Course process/path in SWAYAM

1. E-tutorial
2. E -content
3. E- discuss
4. Evaluation

Objective of Study

1. To study the concept of SWAYAM online course introduced by MHRD and also to find out the different types of certificates course
2. To study the level of awareness about SWAYAM among the students and teachers in different learning path.

Sources of Data Collection

1. Primary Data
2. Secondary Data

Primary Data: A structured questionnaire was prepared and distributed to number of respondents to collect information.

Secondary Data: Information was collected from available published reports and SWAYAM Website.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1) Chart showing age group of respondents

Out of 61 responses the 89% of respondents are in the age group of 20-30 ,6.6 % in the age group of 30-40an 6.6% of the responds are in the age group of 41and above.c

Out of the total respondents 45.9 % are males and 54.1% are females.

2) Chart showing respondents opinion on digitalization and its effectiveness teaching learning process

Out of the total respondents 96.7% are of the opinion that digitalization is effective in the teaching learning process

3) Chart showing respondents who likes to use digital technology in the classroom.

98.4% are Optioned that they would like to use digital technology in the class room.

4) Chart showing why the respondents dislike the usage of technology in the classroom

47% are responds they given reason for not using technology in classroom because of not available and 30.6% are given reason believe in traditional methods others are 22.2% because of lack of technical skills

5) Chart showing the percentage of usage

50.8% respondents are they would like to use technology in classroom 20-40%. 26.2% people like to use in class room 70-100% .18% are like just 20 -40% of adopt digital classes, remaining 6% are don't like to use digital class.

6) chart showing does digital education helps slow learners

80.3% of the respondents opened that digital education would help the slow learners .and 19.7% respondents said that it would not help.

7) Chart showing how the respondents know about online education system

77.1 % said that they have know about online teaching and learning process .and others 22.9 % people they don't know about any online teaching process.

8) Chart showing the respondents who have taken any other education course

76.3% respondents have already taken courses in online.

9) Chart showing for which level of students education is appropriate

The respondents have varied option on application of digital education system, 8.2 of respondents feel the digital system should be introduced in school level 27%.9% feelit should be introduced UG and PG level. 1.6% should be introduced in research and 62.3 % feel it should be introduced in all level of education.

10) Chart showing the respondents who are aware about swayam- MOOCs online application

64.6% are not aware about SWAYAM Online application 35.4 are aware of SWAYAM

11) Chart showing the respondents who likes to use SWAYAY for gaining knowledge and professional development

Respondents have shown readiness to gain knowledge and develop professionally using SWAYAM

12) Chart showing of the respondents who are enrolled for any other course in SWAYAM

26.4% Are respondents have enrolled themselves for varies SWAYAM courses and remaining all not have any enrolment in SWAYAM..

13) chart showing the respondents who likes to recommend SWAYAM to others

All of the respondents 91.8 are said that they would recommends the course to others.

Conclusion

From the primary data collected it can be concluded that respondents are aware of the digital technology, its use in teaching and learning process and its effectiveness. From the survey conducted it was found that there is very little awareness about SWAYAM Online education. The government of India has taken initiative in education and is trying to help the students in varies ways, but there is not people promotion of the SWAYAM APP.

References

1. About Swayam ,Central- Initiative By: Mhrd.
2. Web : [Www.swayam.gov.in](http://www.swayam.gov.in)
3. Free Mooc Couses At Swayam – Govt’s Online Education Platform / Shiksha
4. Web :[Www.shiksha.com](http://www.shiksha.com)
5. Analytical Study Of Swayam –Research Paper
6. Anuva Samanta
7. Phd Research Scholar, Wbuttepa, Kolkata
8. Swayam –A Way Learning - Research Paper
9. Dr.kirti Matliwal Vnsju Surat
10. Web: [Www.ijetmas.com](http://www.ijetmas.com)
- 11.Swayam Mobile Application